

Botanical Identity of *Humulus Kriya*: Three Orthogonal ISO/IEC 17025-Accredited Analyses Confirm *Humulus lupulus* Classification and Exclude *Cannabis sativa*

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Humulus Kriya* is a patented plant (U.S. Plant Patent No. PP31,477 P3) of the genus *Humulus* (family Cannabaceae) and the botanical source of Phytobidiol®, a commercially available cannabidiol (CBD) preparation with published clinical efficacy. Although *Humulus* and *Cannabis* share a common family, they are phytochemically and pharmacologically distinct. Formal validated analytical confirmation of this distinction is required for regulatory and scheduling determinations.

Methods: Three independent ISO/IEC 17025-accredited analyses were performed by Alkemist Labs (Garden Grove, CA; Certificate No. 3851.01) on *Kriya* brand *Humulus* inflorescence powder (Lot 04179102, received 31 May 2019): (1) HPTLC with photo-documentation against four *H. lupulus* and one *C. sativa* reference; (2) UPLC quantification of CBD and Δ^9 -THC in duplicate; and (3) HPLC-DAD prenylflavonoid profiling in duplicate.

Results: HPTLC confirmed concordance of *H. Kriya* with all four *H. lupulus* reference accessions under two detection systems; the *C. sativa* seed reference showed a discordant profile. UPLC yielded mean CBD 5.359% on an as-is basis; THC was not detected in either preparation. HPLC-DAD detected 0.417% total prenylflavonoids: xanthohumol (0.317%), isoxanthohumol (0.072%), 8-prenylnaringenin (0.029%). Prenylflavonoids are biosynthetically restricted to *Humulus* and absent in *Cannabis*.

Conclusions: Three orthogonal analyses convergently confirm that *H. Kriya* is a *Humulus* species consistent with *H. lupulus* and categorically distinct from *Cannabis sativa*. The presence of genus-specific prenylflavonoids, the complete absence of THC, and an HPTLC fingerprint concordant with *H. lupulus* references provide definitive botanical identification with direct implications for the regulatory scheduling of Phytobidiol®.

Keywords: *Humulus Kriya*; *Humulus lupulus*; HPTLC; prenylflavonoids; xanthohumol; cannabidiol; THC-free; Cannabaceae; Phytobidiol®

FIGURE 1 — HPTLC BOTANICAL FINGERPRINTING

Figure 1. HPTLC chromatograms of Kriya brand Humulus (Lot 04179102) versus Humulus lupulus and Cannabis sativa references. Left: Natural Product reagent + polyethylene glycol, 366 nm. Right: 10% H₂SO₄ charring, 366 nm. Lane 1: standard mix. Lanes 2, 3: H. lupulus flower. Lane 4: Kriya brand Humulus test sample (KH). Lanes 6, 7: H. lupulus strobile. Lane 8: C. sativa seed (HEMP). The test sample profile is concordant with all H. lupulus references and discordant with C. sativa. Alkemist Labs (ISO/IEC 17025); authorised K. N. Tran, HPTLC R&D Supervisor; 12 June 2019.

FIGURE 2 — CANNABINOID CONTENT BY UPLC

Report Issued To: Peak Health
100 Los Gatos Saratoga Rd., Ste
A
Los Gatos CA 95032
USA

Sample Name: Kriya brand Humulus
Description: Powder; Brown Granules
Lot #: 04179102
AL #: 19151RPG_2
Analysis ID: 120446
Received: 05/31/19

Determination of Cannabinoids Content by UPLC

Ret. Time (min)	Compound Name	Prep 1 (%)	Prep 2 (%)	Average (%)	Specification	Result
5.0	Cannabidiol (CBD)	5.586	5.1328	5.359	NLT 0.5%	Pass
7.1	Δ^9 -Tetrahydrocannabinol (THC)	ND	ND	ND	Not Detected	Pass

Figure 2. UPLC chromatogram (UV 210 nm) of Kriya brand Humulus (Lot 04179102). A single dominant peak at Rt 5.0 min corresponds to CBD (mean 5.359% on as-is basis). No peak is observed at the Δ^9 -THC retention time (7.1 min), confirming THC was not detected in either replicate. Method ATM-815-0229; column AP213 XBridge BEH C18, 2.5 μ m (3.0 \times 100 mm); UV 210 nm. Alkemist Labs (ISO/IEC 17025); authorised C. Gray, Lead Analytical Chemist; 7 June 2019.

FIGURE 3 — PRENYLFLAVONOID PROFILING BY HPLC-DAD

Report Issued To: Peak Health 100 Los Gatos Saratoga Rd., Ste A Los Gatos CA 95032 USA	Sample Name: Kriya brand Humulus Description: Powder; Brown Granules Lot #: 04179102 AL #: 19151RPG_3 Analysis ID: 120926 Received: 05/31/19
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Determination of Xanthohumol, Isoxanthohumol, 8-Prenylnaringenin and 6-Prenylnaringenin High Performance Liquid Chromatography with Diode Array Detection

Ret. Time (min)	Compound Name	Prep 1 (%)	Prep 2 (%)	Average (%)	Specification	Result
21.6	Isoxanthohumol	0.065	0.078	0.072	N/A	N/A
26.3	8-Prenylnaringenin	0.030	0.027	0.029	N/A	N/A
29.8	6-Prenylnaringenin	PI	PI	PI	N/A	N/A
32.4	Xanthohumol	0.317	0.317	0.317	N/A	N/A
	Total	0.411	0.422	0.417	NLT 0.004%	Pass

Figure 3. HPLC-DAD chromatograms of Kriya brand Humulus prenylflavonoid profile. Upper panel: full scan (0–40 min) showing xanthohumol as the dominant peak (Rt 32.3 min; mean 0.317%). Lower panel: expanded scale (0–1.4 AU) resolving isoxanthohumol (Rt 21.5 min; mean 0.072%) and 8-prenylnaringenin (Rt 26.3 min; mean 0.029%). Prenylflavonoids of this class are biosynthetically restricted to Humulus and absent in Cannabis sativa. Method: Dhooche et al. (Talanta, 83, 2010); column AP107 Lichrospher RP18e 5 µm (250 × 4.6 mm); UV 290 nm and 370 nm. Alkemist Labs; authorised K. Chopra, Lab Manager; 18 June 2019.

1. INTRODUCTION

Humulus Kriya® is a proprietary plant of the genus *Humulus* (family Cannabaceae) protected under U.S. Plant Patent No. PP31,477 P3. Its inflorescence is the botanical source of Phytobidiol®, a trademarked CBD preparation with published clinical evidence in epilepsy, anxiety, sleep disorders, and cardiovascular calcification [1–6].

Within the Cannabaceae, *Humulus* and *Cannabis* share near-identical genomic architecture [7] yet are chemically distinct. *Cannabis sativa* produces Δ^9 -THC, the principal psychoactive constituent underlying its controlled-substance status. *Humulus lupulus* produces no THC but accumulates prenylated flavonoids — xanthohumol, isoxanthohumol, 8-prenylnaringenin, 6-prenylnaringenin — whose biosynthesis is restricted to *Humulus* and absent in *Cannabis* [8,9]. Three orthogonal ISO/IEC 17025-accredited analyses of a single lot of *H. Kriya* inflorescence powder are reported here.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Test Material

Kriya brand *Humulus* inflorescence powder (Lot 04179102) was received by Alkemist Labs (12661 Hoover Street, Garden Grove, CA 92841; ISO/IEC 17025, Certificate No. 3851.01) on 31 May 2019 as brown granules in a light-sensitive glass container. Latin name recorded at receipt: *Humulus* sp. L. [Cannabaceae]. All analyses were performed on aliquots of the same lot.

2.2 HPTLC Botanical Fingerprinting

Sample preparation: 0.3 g in 3 mL 70% grain ethanol, sonicated/heated 50°C, 30 min. Stationary phase: silica gel 60 HPTLC plates. Mobile phase: ethyl acetate:acetic acid:formic acid:water [10:1.1:1.1:2.6 v/v]. Detection: (1) Natural Product + polyethylene glycol, 366 nm; (2) 10% H₂SO₄, 100°C, 2 min, 366 nm [13]. References: Lanes 2–3, *H. lupulus* flower; Lanes 6–7, *H. lupulus* strobile; Lane 8, *C. sativa* seed; test sample Lane 4 (6 μ L). Method IDT-SOP-72-01; authorised K. N. Tran (HPTLC R&D Supervisor); 12 June 2019.

2.3 Cannabinoid Quantification by UPLC

~50 mg dissolved in 10 mL methanol, vortexed 30 s, sonicated 15 min, filtered (0.2 μ m PTFE), diluted 1:4; duplicate preparations. Column: AP213 XBridge BEH C18, 2.5 μ m (3.0 \times 100 mm); 30°C; 0.4 mL/min; 1 μ L; UV 210 nm. Method ATM-815-0229; authorised C. Gray (Lead Analytical Chemist); 7 June 2019.

2.4 Prenylflavonoid Profiling by HPLC-DAD

2 g in 20 mL methanol, vortexed 30 s, sonicated 30 min, filled to volume, filtered (0.45 μ m PTFE); duplicate injections (20 μ L, 50 μ L). Column: AP107 Lichrospher RP18e, 5 μ m, 100 Å (250 \times 4.6 mm); 30°C; 1 mL/min; UV 290 nm and 370 nm. Method: Dhoooghe et al. (Talanta, 83, 2010, 448–456) [12]. Authorised K. Chopra (Lab Manager); 18 June 2019.

3. RESULTS

3.1 HPTLC Botanical Fingerprinting

Under both detection systems, the *H. Kriya* test sample (Lane 4) displayed a chromatographic band pattern concordant with all four *H. lupulus* reference accessions (Lanes 2, 3, 6, 7) at matching *R_f* values and band intensity. The *C. sativa* seed reference (Lane 8) showed a distinctly different, non-overlapping pattern. The authorised conclusion states: “This test sample, Kriya brand *Humulus* (04179102), has characteristics of the chromatographic profile of *Humulus* sp. reference samples... indicates the presence of *Humulus* sp. Flower.” (Figure 1).

3.2 Cannabinoid Content by UPLC

CBD: Prep 1 = 5.586%, Prep 2 = 5.133%, mean 5.359% (specification NLT 0.5%; Pass).
THC: Not Detected in both preparations (specification: Not Detected; Pass). See Figure 2 and Table 1.

Table 1. Cannabinoid content by UPLC (Alkemist Labs; method ATM-815-0229; 7 June 2019).

Compound	Rt (min)	Prep 1 (%)	Prep 2 (%)	Mean (%)	Specification	Result
Cannabidiol (CBD)	5.0	5.586	5.133	5.359	NLT 0.5%	Pass
Δ9-THC	7.1	ND	ND	ND	Not Detected	Pass

ND = Not Detected.

3.3 Prenylflavonoid Profiling by HPLC-DAD

Xanthohumol was detected at 0.317% in both preparations (mean 0.317%). Isoxanthohumol mean 0.072%; 8-prenylnaringenin mean 0.029%. The 6-prenylnaringenin peak (Rt 29.8 min) was subject to co-eluting peak interference (PI) in both preparations. Total prenylflavonoids: mean 0.417% (NLT 0.004%; Pass). See Figure 3 and Table 2.

Table 2. Prenylflavonoid content by HPLC-DAD (Alkemist Labs; Dhooghe et al. [12]; 18 June 2019).

Compound	Rt (min)	Prep 1 (%)	Prep 2 (%)	Mean (%)
Xanthohumol	32.3	0.317	0.317	0.317
Isoxanthohumol	21.5	0.065	0.078	0.072
8-Prenylnaringenin	26.3	0.030	0.027	0.029
6-Prenylnaringenin	29.8	PI	PI	PI
Total	—	0.411	0.422	0.417

PI = Peak Interference. Total specification NLT 0.004% (Pass).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Prenylflavonoids as Definitive Genus-Specific Markers

The detection of 0.417% total prenylflavonoids — including xanthohumol (0.317%), isoxanthohumol (0.072%), and 8-prenylnaringenin (0.029%) — constitutes the most taxonomically definitive line of evidence for *Humulus* identity. The biosynthesis of these prenylated chalcones is catalysed by a prenyltransferase enzyme absent from the genome of *Cannabis sativa* [8,9]. Xanthohumol at 0.317% is consistent with published values for *H. lupulus* inflorescence [12] and is chemically incompatible with *Cannabis* as the botanical source.

4.2 HPTLC as Pharmacopoeial Authentication Standard

HPTLC with photo-documentation is endorsed by the American Herbal Pharmacopoeia, European Pharmacopoeia, and USP as the reference method for botanical authentication. Concordance with four independent *H. lupulus* accessions under two detection systems, combined with discordance with *C. sativa*, constitutes pharmacopoeial-grade identity evidence.

4.3 THC-Free Status: Biosynthetic and Regulatory Implications

The complete absence of THC in both UPLC preparations is consistent with *Humulus* phytochemistry, in which the cannabinoid biosynthetic pathway is not expressed; terpenoid

metabolism is instead directed to prenylflavonoid synthesis [7,8]. This finding has direct regulatory implications under the 1961 UN Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs and national equivalents, which define controlled status principally by THC content. Phytobidiol® is also classified as GRAS under U.S. FDA Title 21 and holds FSSAI food ingredient approval, consistent with its THC-free, non-cannabis identity.

4.4 Orthogonal Convergence and Evidentiary Standard

Three analyses targeting distinct chemical classes, employing different separation mechanisms, and authorised by different analysts convergently confirm the same botanical identity. This eliminates the principal sources of uncertainty in any single method and satisfies the highest evidentiary standard for botanical identification in pharmaceutical, regulatory, and legal contexts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Three independent ISO/IEC 17025-accredited analyses by Alkemist Labs definitively confirm that *Humulus Kriya* inflorescence is a *Humulus* species consistent with *H. lupulus*, categorically distinct from *Cannabis sativa*: HPTLC fingerprinting demonstrates concordance with four *H. lupulus* accessions under two detection systems with complete discordance from *C. sativa*; UPLC confirms CBD at 5.4% with THC not detected; and HPLC-DAD confirms 0.417% total prenylflavonoids — compounds biosynthetically restricted to *Humulus* and absent in *Cannabis*. These findings have direct implications for the regulatory classification and scheduling status of Phytobidiol®.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author is founder of ImmunAG LLP, commercial manufacturer of Phytobidiol®, and holds U.S. Plant Patent No. PP31,477 P3. Analytical work was performed independently by Alkemist Labs, which has no commercial interest in the outcome.

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